
Power Meditation Coaching Processes and Stages – A Silhouette. What a Meditation Psychologist Handles?

Ramesh Kumar G S

Consulting and Meditation Psychologist, Wonderfeelz Neuropsychology Studio, Coimbatore, India

ABSTRACT

Neuropsychology Power meditation is entirely different from all other meditations in vogue. This meditation has been developed to help people with Goal-Oriented system in an individualized manner and for the persons who have many drawbacks such as lacking time to spend on meditation, severe stress, and body conditions not conducive for traditional padmasana position. This meditation can be done only for few seconds at a time and can be done even while at hectic tasks by a person after undergoing proper coaching.

This uses certain processes and configured systematically. The processes involved are already being used by the current author and now need to be recorded and documented systematically for academic and clinical purposes. The processes have been evolved based on the scientific psychology and heritage.

In the current paper, author has narrated those processes briefly as to be outlined. The processes included cover the stages that occur initially through the final stage, as of now being practiced by the current author. This paper narrates three important founding principles, and around ten processes involved along with the differences when compared to other meditation systems.

Keywords: Neuropsychology Power Meditation, Attention-Breathing Dissociation, Core Feel, Self-Imposed Conditions, Guessing,

1. Introduction

Neuropsychology Power meditation is entirely different from all other meditations in vogue. This meditation has been developed to help people with Goal-Oriented system in an individualized manner and for the persons who have many drawbacks such as lacking time to spend on meditation, severe stress, and body conditions not conducive for traditional Padmasana position. This meditation can be done only for few seconds at a time and can be done even while at hectic tasks by a person after undergoing proper coaching.

In this paper the processes and stages involved in Wonderfeelz Neuropsychology Power meditation are outlined comparing with existing objective knowledge.

Wonderfeelz Neuropsychology Power Meditation is a technique operates on three important principles:

Empowering mind – mind has the natural capacity to process information, calculate and regulate oneself without his conscious efforts. It is the natural power to get his logic convinced for what suitable to him and thereby making those suitable options as his preferred options or aims in life.

As the mind is empowered, his ***Mind Rightly Self-Regulates*** individuals without their awareness or preference and become instrumental towards those suitable things. This gives a feeling of “God Guides Rightly”. So, more he allows his mind to exercise its natural power, the more he becomes contented with incremental perceptions of “God Guides Rightly”, operationally God is the natural regulatory power of his own mind, (and so far, none saw any God).

Individuals should avoid imposing conditions onto their mind and ***allow mind to operate naturally***. Self-Impositions that become valuable in the eyes of his reference group and not his uniqueness, can drive individuals away from originality and what actually they actually are. Making the mind guide the person rather than he imposes conditions and compulsions onto the mind is a way of life. It is essential to Rediscover one’s own originality and thereby enhance his unique competitiveness in his life

2. Basic Processes:

Basic processes and stages involved in the system of Wonderfeelz Neuropsychology Power meditation, start with Preparation and pass through stages to reach the final stage of effortless meditation.

2.1 Preparation:

In the current system of meditation, the learners are first put on relaxation technique using guessing and then only meditation coaching is begun. The relaxation technique used will first help the learner to 'enter' the meditative process and negate anxiety if any related to meditative experiences. Sankalp is also a process of resolution but described clearly elsewhere (Ramesh Kumar G S 2022a).

2.2 Breathing:

Breathing is continuously monitored as a parameter in understanding the person and his efforts during his learning. Coaching essentially notes the breathing and intervened. In the current system breathing and attention are correlated, as when the learners try to focus attention without efforts, the breathing would be normal, while they become meticulous due to cognitions related to time urgency or perfection, then arresting of breathing occurs involuntarily. This relation between attention and breathing is recently proved by the finding that breathing and attention are two 'giant' mechanisms that go hand-in-hand and carry on their 'shoulders' the whole cognition (Mitsea, Eleni., Drigas, Athanasios., Skianis, Charalampos 2022).

Importantly the Breathing and Attention correlation mediated through effortfulness is well recognized in this system and altered to dissociate to the extent, the negative interactions between the two are nullified. This effortfulness mediated correlation of breathing and attention is found in any voluntary task, and needs to be checked for its negative consequences.

2.3 Attention:

Attention is one of the very first attributes a new born tries to establish to get his needs satisfied from the environment. As the child grows, the behaviours initiated by self toward environment and vice versa, engages the tool of attention primarily and as foundation. Attention pervades far and wide of psychological functions such as information processing, Emotion regulation, social cognition (Dolcos, Florin, et.al 2020) and behavioural self-control (Duckworth, Angela L et.al 2019).

Attention is claimed to be volition. 'For if one kind of attention is volition, namely attention to an idea, it would seem that must be the voluntary attention' (Shand, A. F. 1896). Though the phenomena associated with attention are assumed into exhaustive list of 'types' Hommel, Bernhard et.al (2019), Psychologists since the time of Wundt have consistently maintained only the distinction of Voluntary and Involuntary while negating other understandings (for example, Prinzmetal, William., McCool, Christin., and Park, Samuel. 2005).

Wonderfeelz Neuropsych Power Meditation system strongly advocates the standard types of Voluntary, Involuntary and Habitual attentions. Meditation deals with voluntary attention. Any meditation starts with regulating attention. The operational definition of meditation (Ramesh Kumar G S 2022a) that is universal to cover any and all kind of meditation efforts also stress on maneuvering voluntary attention.

2.4 Voluntary Attention

Voluntary attention is a strongly placed attribute that determines success in one's mission or intention. This is common to any organism as predators increase the probability of predation by their voluntary attention (Knudsen EI 2018). Voluntary attention is determined by anticipatory information (Bugg, Julie., Crump, Matthew 2012) and anticipation triggered by perceived emotional expressions Folyi, T., Rohr, M., & Wentura, D. (2020).

Emotional content enhances both covert and overt shifts of attention and such shifts differ but are comparably affected by emotional content too (Kulke, Louisa., Brümmer, Lena., Pooresmaeli, Arezoo., Schacht, Anne 2021), thus making attention and attention shift an intricate aspect.

In the brain, P300 amplitude of the attention target is larger than the P300 amplitude of the un-attention target in the selective and switching attention conditions; the P300 amplitude of the two targets that were simultaneously attended, was not significantly different, in the divided attention condition (Honoki, Yuto et.al, 2021). Frontal theta power changes according to task of attention that an increase is observed (starting at ~500 ms post cue) for voluntary attention relative to instructed attention. Posterior alpha power lateralization was delayed in voluntary attention relative to instructed attention, and the amount of delay was related to the timing of frontal theta increase, the increase due to conflict resolution and decision-making aspects of willed attention (Rajan, Abhijit et.al, 2019).

Here the current author feels appropriate to point out that most of his clients who underwent relaxation therapy and expected to do at home on their own had reported that they used to get better results when the instructions were given by the current author and not equally satisfied with their own self-initiated practice at home.

2.5 Preference For Non-Sensory Stimuli

Anticipatory information can either increase or decrease attention to meaning of upcoming stimuli in the mind. When anticipatory information either decreases attention to, or decreases negative meaning of, upcoming unpleasant stimuli, subsequently lead to down-regulation goal to decrease attention or negative meaning, resulting in low regulatory challenge. However, when anticipatory information either enhances attention to, or enhances negative meaning of, upcoming unpleasant stimuli, it subsequently leads to conflicts with a counter down-regulation goal to decrease attention or negative meaning (i.e., no fit), resulting in high regulatory challenge (Shafir, Roni and Sheppes, Gal, 2020).

Anticipatory information in visual perception is strong and therefore meditation psychologist should educate the meditation learner to eyes closed condition be preferred to ensure better control over the anticipation and voluntary attention. Attention changes the visual appearance of attended stimuli across a variety of perceptual domains, such as contrast, spatial frequency, and colour, and visual attention not only changes our neural representations, but that it can actually affect what we think we see (Sam Ling 2012).

Effect of reward acted independently of voluntary attention, reward and task-relevance independently influence stimulus processing in visual cortex (Buschsulte et al., 2014; Garcia-Lazaro et al., 2019), while effect of reward history on visual processing is independent from voluntary attention (Anderson, 2016; Failing & Theeuwes, 2017). Meditation learners do experience acceptance for 'no happy / neutral feel' they get. In fact, they perceive the meditation is effective due to this 'no happy / neutral feel'.

In a study (Mrkva, K., Westfall, J., & Van Boven, L. 2019), participants repeatedly directed attention toward a target object during sequential search, and subsequently perceived their emotional reactions to target objects as more intense than their reactions to control objects. Tendency to perceive spatially cued objects as more emotionally intense than noncued objects, are found, even after mental rehearsal of the name of noncued objects. These intricacies borne in mind and visual stimuli are less preferred for meditation over non-sensory objects.

Interaction between endogenous and exogenous spatial attention lead to some contingent effect on Perceptual results. Exogenous attention mechanically modulates task performance during information accrual, both when endogenous attention has been pre-allocated to the target location and when it is distributed across the visual scene. With enough time, however, a focused attention system can render negligible the exogenous effect of irrelevant onsets (Grubb, Michael & White, Alex & Heeger, David & Carrasco, Marisa.2015).

This same exogenous time required, causing anxiety and disappointment to the meditation learners when they interpret such a lead time as reflecting their severity of problem or inability to enter meditation state. This is a perceived response and subjective interpretation need to be identified and addressed by the meditation psychologist. Studies like mentioned above indicate such a lead time is a natural and normal entity, but the maladaptive mind responds neurotically to it.

Thus, in the current meditation system, there is a parallel travel of meditation coaching and supportive psychological working through – making this an Intervention Meditation system. Such a therapeutic procedure necessitates individual setting for meditation coaching, unlike the possible group setting in all other meditation systems.

Meditation Psychologist plays the crucial role as a psychologist to identify the kind of process enhancing or decreasing and attention or meaning of upcoming stimuli, again unobtrusively. The most crucial role or most critical role of the psychologist here is to ensure such manoeuvring is not suppression of negative emotions or thoughts to form only additional pathology.

Attention coupled with preferences indicate the emotionality of the individuals (Harrison, Ashley J., and Gibb, Brandon E 2015; Oliver, A., Pile, V., Elm, D. et al 2019). Emotional bond with the distractors, fixation and preferences has psychological significance for the concerned individual. He is encouraged to do meditation and aware of the emotional bond without getting trapped by the bonded emotions. While emotional bond is producing awareness into the kind of emotion linking the individual's self with the particular object of distraction or fixation or preference, the bonded emotion is the obsessive emotion that prevents one to get out of the emotional bond and thus bonded emotion is a dynamic involved in emotional bond making it stronger.

Hence, in the current method of meditation, this fact is utilized for understanding the individual's emotionality with a diagnostic bent of mind and towards understanding possible emotional dynamics unobtrusively. This is done judiciously by the qualified and experienced psychologist, that such unobtrusive psychological work through of emotional dynamics of the meditation learner by the meditation psychologist is an essential component of the meditation coaching process.

In meditation of any sort, especially in the current system of meditation, non-visual stimuli are suggested for meditating purpose. To distinguish from other meditations, the current system focuses on non-emotional and non-sensory meditation object (here the word object refers to anything and even abstract, upon which attention is focused for meditating purpose). It is an intricate juncture to understand the non-sensory and non-emotional stimulus as meditative object.

2.6 Distractors and Fixations To Be Worked-Through

Anticipatory tendency /Expectancy effect, Compensation, Observation, Comparison, Contrasting, Verification, time urgency, tendency to take short-cut, complacency are some of the most discouraged processes for a learner by the meditation psychologist due to their potential to block progressive development of meditation skill and stages. Meditation Psychologist has the responsibility to identify these intricate troubles and rectify as part of coaching. Preferences also do intertwine with distractors within the mind of the meditation learner. Psychologists are well aware that such fixations are tendencies and are neuropsychological. The meditation psychologist in this system of meditation, therefore need to be well experienced beside core qualification in psychology. The meditation coaching in this current system of meditation, is therefore diagnostic and intervention every instance. This is the reason the current author asks the meditation learner to follow the instruction for only couple of minutes maximum at a time and asks feedback only to be worked-through psychologically.

The observation of body languages during the minutes, the learner attempts to follow the instructions are crucial and need to be interpreted along with feedback given by learner after every couple of minutes. In an attempt to address if proactively inhibiting salient distractors can prevent attentional capture, selection history overpowered any effects of voluntary goals, that observers were unable to avoid fixating a salient distractor irrespective of whether it was a target earlier, or observer had voluntarily chosen this colour to be the distractor colour just moments before (Nicholas Gaspelin, John M. Gaspar & Steven J. Luck2019).

Thus, the past history of the distracting thoughts occupies a crucial place in the coaching process in the current system of meditation. It should be notable that such past histories of potential distractors are emotionally significant and often controlled by the subconscious and or unconscious. Amateur or quackery attempt to handle those distractors and their history would lead to potential harm to the meditation learners. This kind of intricate situations are ignored in other meditation systems or left to take their own course, in each individual.

In another study (Lilla M. Gurtner, Walter F. Bischof, Fred W. Mast, 2019), fixation locations during imagery were related to those during perception. Participants also showed the tendency to return more often to areas they had previously looked at during imagery along with their scan paths more clustered and more repetitive when compared to visual perception. Sooner after initial fixation during mental imagery. Refixations of the same area do occur.

This is especially intricate when the meditation is administered to an individual having interpersonal issues, as interpersonal issues are composed of more abstract concepts than concrete ones. Associating verbal concepts with visual images are more difficult with Abstract Concepts than with Concrete Concepts (Fini C, Era V, Da Rold F, Candidi M, Borghi AM. 2021) necessitating more hints with Abstract Concepts than Concrete Concepts and are more synchronous.

On one side, as the learner gets insight into his life situations, behaviours and thought processes would seek more clarity from the meditation psychologist and on the other hand, when the salient distractors with the past history are worked-through during the coaching phase by the meditation psychologist, the learner would require handle more abstract and concrete concepts – that again to be worked-through only psychologically and not by lay theories. It should be strongly borne in mind by any professional that the responses, behaviours, doubts, fears etc of a learner have deep rooted psychological significance and must not be treated according to convenience of the handler.

2.7 Individual Differences:

Variations in lapses of attention are partially attributable to individual differences. Individuals do differ in their ability to voluntarily control the intensity of attention (intrinsic alertness) and fully engage preparatory processes on a moment-by-moment basis. Those particularly susceptible to lapses of attention (indexed by the slowest response times) demonstrated a decreased pupillary response during the interstimulus interval, whereas individuals less susceptible to lapses of attention demonstrated an increased pupillary response during the interstimulus interval (Unsworth, N., Miller, A. L., & Robison, M. K. 2020).

Current Meditation system gives utmost importance to individual differences in every aspect starting from needs, current life situations, strengths, weaknesses, of the individual through various processes and principles involved till the stage of effortless meditation. Hence, Wonderfeelz Neuropsychology Power meditation can not be given for even two persons together by the same meditation psychologist during the same time-slot.

Even mental imagery is a simulation of perception, and provide evidence consistent with the supportive role of eye movement in neural reactivation (Michael B Bone, Marie St-Laurent, Christa Dang, Douglas A McQuiggan, Jennifer D Ryan, Bradley R Buchsbaum, 2019). Specific neural reactivation of vivid imagery and with memory for stimulus image details correlate positively. Image-specific eye movements accompany image-specific patterns of brain activity during visualization. It is clear that not only in eyes open condition, but also the eyes closed condition such as in meditation lend chance for potential distractors and their history relevant to the concerned individual emotionally.

2.8 Guessing

Guessing and not imagination is employed in the current system of meditation for initial relaxation and orientation development purposes. The current system of meditation does not employ any counter-reality for sake of therapeutic purposes, but employs only the naturally occurring phenomena are made use of. The meditation learners are not left completely without control, but with clarity during coaching. It is important that the meditation psychologist ensures only a pure guessing process rather than imaginations and verifies with the psychological principles that characterize the guessing as distinct from intuition and imagination.

In guessing, instead of imagination as done by others, the meditation learner does guess the actual but not imagining something that is absent. While, imagination is unreality oriented, guessing is reality oriented. Consistency between behaviour and electrophysiological oscillations (alpha and beta bands) are biomarkers for decoding the phrase-guessing procedure (Zhao, J., Zhang, Y., Qin, Y. et al . 2022). Guessing should be done with some precautions (Wise, S.L. 2017). The dynamics involved in guessing to be monitored for enhancing effectiveness of the technique and purpose. The timing, cognitions before and during guessing, attitude toward guessing ability of oneself, complacency, expectancy effect, tendency to hurry or take short-cut, all would determine the guessing technique used in relaxation and meditation under the current system of meditation.

Guessing is deliberate reasoning process activity rooted in biological instinct and a response to a perceptual judgment of a problem as a problematic situation or fact (Tschaeppe, Mark 2014). Hence, there is a mental activity akin to actual though he or she is not directly observing through sense organs. Subthalamic Nucleus (STN) local field potential (LFP) carries information about intended force generation even in the absence of actual muscle activity or movement-related peripheral proprioceptive feedback, in addition to finding out for the first time that increased STN gamma activity during motor imagery, and shows that the increase of gamma activity in the STN is not only associated with actual movement or muscle activation (Petra Fischer et.al 2017)..

Meditators show altered engagement of neural regions related to attention, including both higher order processes generated by frontal regions, and sensory anticipation processes generated by posterior regions. This activity may reflect an increased capacity to modulate a range of neural processes in order to meet task requirements. This increased capacity may underlie the improved attentional function observed in mindfulness meditators (Bailey NW, Freedman G, Raj K, Sullivan CM, Rogasch NC, Chung SW, et al. 2019). It has to be made clear if this altered engagement and improved attentional function could lead to self-validating task and a scenario similar to delayed Posterior alpha power lateralization related to the timing of frontal theta increase discussed already in this paper.

While this process during meditation to be addressed scientifically by qualified meditation psychologists, another challenge is not falling prey to so-called 'brief meditations'. Brief meditations are not strongly supported as the changes reported are only on the self-reported stress levels and not parametric (Colgary, Christina., Dong, Shengli and Fisher, Paige. 2020).

The current meditation system is based on the Theory of Progressive Stages which assume that everything occurs in stage-wise manner, comprising of either primary stages or secondary stages (Ramesh Kumar, G S 1999). Hence, the concept of 'brief' is not acceptable as sound. Moreover, the current system of meditation is strongly grounded on recognizing individual differences at every minute instance and responding to the intricacy in a due manner.

2.9 Conditions are Self-generated and self-imposed

While one is engaged in meditation, and expected to have control over thoughts, it is natural that such a person gets many self-generated conditions reflected through self-generated thoughts. The self-generated conditions reflected through self-generated thoughts are already set to thwart his mental peace and concentration. The individual is expected to control such thoughts in other forms of meditation, the current system expects him not to engage with thoughts at all. Multi-factor analysis (MFA) of self-generated thoughts revealed three dimensions of thought content: self-referential thought,

negative thoughts about one's surroundings, and thoughts in the form of imagery with corresponding neural correlates (Brennan, D, Murrough, JW, Morris, LS, 2021). Similarly, stress could also be self-imposed and not only others imposed (Wang, D., Tian, L., Hou, Z., Zhou, J.-P., Zhao, A., & Zhang, H. 2023). The self-constraints include Reflective Self-Limiting also (Ramesh Kumar G S 2022b).

In the current system these are tapped without encouraging to focus on and be mindful about these hurdles. The feel process alone is encouraged, while the psychologist interprets the hurdles psychologically, to the learner. Thus, the learner is not a passive observer nor the trainer is. Both are active in their respective processes, while the psychologist is clearly involved in (i) working-through psychologically, (ii) coaching and (iii) leading.

2.10 Core Feel:

In the current system, the psychologist encourages the learner only to practice experiencing and attending to, 'Core Feel'. Core feel has already indicated by the current author in his earlier paper (Ramesh Kumar G S 2022a) and is different from Mindfulness.

The continuous process results in various automatic positive changes / self-growth within the person and 'effortless meditation'. The positive changes / self-growth different from person to person in all respects. Importantly, the changes including the one consequent to Sankalp, are occurring without planning or control of the person but automatically. Ultimately *Feel Heals*.

3. Discussion

In the current paper, the processes and stages involved in the Wonderfeelz Neuropsych Power meditation have been outlined. This is only small effort towards outlining the components. This paper is part of the sequence of papers being published on the Neuropsych Power meditation system. There are at least 10 important aspects the meditation psychologist has to take care of.

The processes though seem to be similar to other meditations, there are fundamental differences between the Wonderfeelz Neuropsych Power Meditation and other meditations. (i) Specific Goal and Preparation, (ii) the Core Feel, (iii) possibility and feasibility of time duration one can spend on meditating at any given point of time, (iv) the working-through that require a psychologist who is qualified to the core of psychology and neuropsychology before becoming a coach on this meditation system, (v) method of mind-control achieved in an effortless manner, (vi) the multitude of benefits, (vii) individualized benefits as guided by the mind of the learner rather than conscious strain for benefits, (viii) fact that this system can not be given to even two persons at the same time slot together by same meditation psychologist, but only one at a time, (ix) identification of self-generation of stress / maladaptability and (x) getting maladaptability corrected in an effortless manner are basic differences between the Wonderfeel Neuropsych Power Meditation and other systems in vogue.

Thus, the current system of meditation makes it possible to have completely measured progress of meditation ability and stages progressively. This helps to course-correct at any earliest point through the coaching by meditation psychologist and get individualized benefits like a surgical strike operation. This is also unique to this system. Intricate psychological processes involved in coaching necessitates a thorough training in core psychology for at least 5 years and a psychologist's bent of mind as a pre-requisite for becoming a coach on this system. Various factors that contribute for the intricacy during coaching to a learner are outlined in this paper.

This system alleviates the demerit of much time required and monotonous practice of other systems, helping especially the high stress and complicated stress segments of Businessmen, Professionals and Politicians.

By merit, this paper clarifies the processes and uniqueness of Wonderfeelz Neuropsych Power Meditation system, while having the demerit being descriptive and experiential rather than experimental data.

References

- Anderson, B. A. (2016). The attention habit: How reward learning shapes attentional selection. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 1369(1), 24–39. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nyas.12957>
- Bailey NW, Freedman G, Raj K, Sullivan CM, Rogasch NC, Chung SW, et al. (2019) Mindfulness meditators show altered distributions of early and late neural activity markers of attention in a response inhibition task. *PLoS ONE* 14(8): e0203096. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0203096>
- Brennan, D, Murrough, JW, Morris, LS (2021): Intrasubject functional connectivity related to self-generated thoughts. *Brain Behav.* ; 11:e01860. <https://doi.org/10.1002/brb3.1860>
- Bugg, Julie., Crump, Matthew (2012): In Support of a Distinction between Voluntary and Stimulus-Driven Control: A Review of the Literature on Proportion Congruent Effects. *Frontiers in psychology*, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2012.00367>
- Buschschulte, A., Boehler, C. N., Strumpf, H., Stoppel, C., Heinze, H.-J., Schoenfeld, M. A., & Hopf, J.-M. (2014). Reward- and Attention-related Biasing of Sensory Selection in Visual Cortex. *Journal of Cognitive Neuroscience*, 26(5), 1049–1065. https://doi.org/10.1162/jocn_a_00539
- Colgary, Christina & Dong, Shengli & Fisher, Paige. (2020). One-Session Mindfulness versus Concentrative Meditation: The Effects of Stress Anticipation. *American Journal of Health Education*. 51. 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19325037.2020.1712668>

- Duckworth, Angela L., Taxer, Jamie L., Eskreis-Winkler, Lauren., Galla, Brian M., and Gross, James J. (2019): Self-Control and Academic Achievement, *Annu. Rev. Psychol.* 70:373–99. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-psych-010418-103230>
- Dolcos, Florin, et.al (2020): Neural correlates of emotion-attention interactions: From perception, learning, and memory to social cognition, individual differences, and training interventions. *Neuroscience and Biobehavioral Reviews*, 108, 559–601. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2019.08.017>
- Failing, M., & Theeuwes, J. (2017). Selection history: How reward modulates selectivity of visual attention. *Psychonomic Bulletin and Review*, 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13423-724017-1380-y>
- Fini C, Era V, Da Rold F, Candidi M, Borghi AM.(2021): Abstract concepts in interaction: the need of others when guessing abstract concepts smooths dyadic motor interactions. *R. Soc. Open Sci.* 8: 201205. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.201205>
- Folyi, T., Rohr, M., & Wentura, D. (2020). When emotions guide your attention in line with a context-specific goal: Rapid utilization of visible and masked emotional faces for anticipatory attentional orienting. *Emotion*, 20(7), 1206–1224. <https://doi.org/10.1037/emo0000621>
- Garcia-Lazaro, H. G., Bartsch, M. V., Boehler, C. N., Krebs, R. M., Donohue, S. E., Harris, J. A., and Hopf, J.-M. (2019). Dissociating Reward- and Attention-driven Biasing of Global Feature-based Selection in Human Visual Cortex. *Journal of Cognitive Neuroscience*, 31(4):1-13. https://doi.org/10.1162/jocn_a_01356
- Grubb, Michael., White, Alex., Heeger, David., and Carrasco, Marisa. (2015). Interactions between voluntary and involuntary attention modulate the quality and temporal dynamics of visual processing. *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review*. 22(2), 437–444 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13423-014-0698-y>
- Harrison, Ashley J., and Gibb, Brandon E (2015): Attentional Biases in Currently Depressed Children: An EyeTracking Study of Biases in Sustained Attention to Emotional Stimuli. *J Clin Child Adolesc Psychol.* 2015 ; 44(6): 1008–1014. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15374416.2014.930688>
- Hommel, Bernhard., Chapman, Craig S., Cisek, Paul ., Neyedli, Heather F., Song, Joo-Hyun., Welsh, Timothy N. (2019): No one knows what attention is. *Attention, Perception, & Psychophysics* , 81:2288–2303. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13414-019-01846-w>
- Honoki, Yuto., Guan, Siqing., Oguchi, Mana., Takahashi, Toru., Nitta, Yusuke., Tomita, Nozomi., and Kumano, Hiroaki. (2021). A method for measuring voluntary attention control with event-related potential P300. 33-34. 279-286. Download page: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/351086048_A_method_for_measuring_voluntary_attention_control_with_event-related_potential_P300/citations
- Knudsen EI (2018): Neural Circuits That Mediate Selective Attention: A Comparative Perspective. *Trends Neurosci.* 2018 Nov;41(11):789-805. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tins.2018.06.006>
- Kulke, Louisa., Brümmer, Lena., Pooresmaeli, Arezoo., Schacht, Anne (2021): Overt and covert attention shifts to emotional faces: Combining EEG, eye tracking, and a go/no-go paradigm, *Psychophysiology*, Vol 58, Issue 8. <https://doi.org/10.1111/psyp.13838>
- Lilla M. Gurtner, Walter F. Bischof, Fred W. Mast (2019): Recurrence quantification analysis of eye movements during mental imagery. *Journal of Vision*;19(1):17. <https://doi.org/10.1167/19.1.17>
- Michael B Bone, Marie St-Laurent, Christa Dang, Douglas A McQuiggan, Jennifer D Ryan, Bradley R Buchsbaum, Eye Movement Reinstatement and Neural Reactivation During Mental Imagery, *Cerebral Cortex*, Volume 29, Issue 3, March 2019, Pages 1075–1089, <https://doi.org/10.1093/cercor/bhy014>
- Mitsea, Eleni., Drigas, Athanasios., Skianis, Charalampos (2022): Breathing, Attention & Consciousness in Sync: The role of Breathing Training, *Metacognition & Virtual Reality*, *Technium Soc. Sci. J.* Vol.29, 79 – 97. <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v29i1.6145>
- Mrkva, K., Westfall, J., & Van Boven, L. (2019). Attention Drives Emotion: Voluntary Visual Attention Increases Perceived Emotional Intensity. *Psychological Science*, 30(6), 942–954. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0956797619844231>
- Nicholas Gaspelin, John M. Gaspar & Steven J. Luck (2019) Oculomotor inhibition of salient distractors: Voluntary inhibition cannot override selection history, *Visual Cognition*, 27:3-4, 227-246, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13506285.2019.1600090>
- Oliver, A., Pile, V., Elm, D. et al. The Cognitive Neuropsychology of Depression in Adolescents. *Curr Behav Neurosci Rep* 6, 227–235 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40473-019-00187-0>
- Petra Fischer et.al (2017): Subthalamic nucleus beta and gamma activity is modulated depending on the level of imagined grip force. *Experimental Neurology*, Volume 293, Pages 53-61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.expneurol.2017.03.0>
- Prinzmetal, William., McCool, Christin., and Park, Samuel (2005): Attention: Reaction Time and Accuracy Reveal Different Mechanisms. *Journal of Experimental Psychology*, Vol. 134, No. 1, 73–92. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0096-3445.134.1.73>
- Rajan, Abhijit., Siegel, Scott N., Liu, Yuelu ., Bengson, Jesse., Mangun, George R., and Ding, Mingzhou (2019): Theta Oscillations Index Frontal Decision-Making and Mediate Reciprocal Frontal–Parietal Interactions in Willed Attention. *Cerebral Cortex*, July 2019; 2832–2843. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cercor/bhy149>

- Ramesh Kumar G S (1999): Ramesh Kumar., G S (1999): Conceptualizations On Human Behaviour; Another Angle Attempted. 86th session of Indian Science Congress Association, 3rd – 7th Jan, 1999. Chennai
- Ramesh Kumar G S (2022a): New Intervention Meditation Combining Heritage and Psychology, *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, 2022, 9(4) pp72-79. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6497610>
- Ramesh Kumar G S (2022b): Extreme Uncertainty And Feeling Of Being Rounded-Up 360 Degrees: Become A Phoenix Using Concepts Of Merged Time Perspective And Reflective Self-Limiting, *Int. Jour of Res Pub and Rev*, Vol 3, issue 7, pp 2399 – 2406. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6845307>
- Sam Ling (2012): Attention alters appearance. *Journal of Vision*, 12(9):1387. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1167/12.9.1387>
- Shafir, Roni and Sheppes, Gal, (2020): How anticipatory information shapes subsequent emotion regulation, *Emotion*, 02, 20, 68-74. <https://doi.org/10.1037/emo0000673>
- Shand, A. F. (1896). Attention and Will: A Study in Involuntary Action. *Philosophical Review* 5:198.
- Tschaeppe, Mark (2014): Guessing and Abduction. *Transactions of the Charles S Peirce Society A Quarterly Journal in American Philosophy* 50(1):115-138. <https://doi.org/10.2979/tranchepeirsoc.50.1.115>
- Unsworth, N., Miller, A. L., & Robison, M. K. (2020). Individual differences in lapses of sustained attention: Oculometric indicators of intrinsic alertness. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Perception and Performance*, 46(6), 569–592. <https://doi.org/10.1037/xhp0000734>
- Wang, D., Tian, L., Hou, Z., Zhou, J.-P., Zhao, A., & Zhang, H. (2023). The Development of an Interpersonal Stressors Scale: Identifying Self-Imposed and Other-Imposed Interpersonal Stressors. *Psychological Reports*, 126(1), 502–526. <https://doi.org/10.1177/003329412111043458>
- Wise, S.L. (2017), Rapid-Guessing Behavior: Its Identification, Interpretation, and Implications. *Educational Measurement: Issues and Practice*, 36: 52-61. <https://doi.org/10.1111/emip.12165>
- Zhao, J., Zhang, Y., Qin, Y. et al. (2022). Electroencephalographic oscillations of alpha and beta rhythms during phrase-guessing procedure. *Cogn Neurodyn* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11571-022-09896-x>